

Table S6. Multivariate mixed-effects logistic regression for *dhfr* and *dhps* mutations in ANC and GP samples (sensitivity analysis)

Odds ratios (OR) with 95% CI and p values are presented (p values <0.05 in bold).

<i>dhfr</i> Fixed effects	N51				C59				S108				Triple <i>dhfr</i>			
	OR	95% CI		<i>P</i>	OR	95% CI		<i>P</i>	OR	95% CI		<i>P</i>	OR	95% CI		<i>P</i>
Age (10 years) †	0.59	0.41	0.84	0.004	0.70	0.48	1.01	0.057	0.78	0.53	1.15	0.213	0.60	0.42	0.86	0.005
Season#	1.06	0.69	1.62	0.798	1.05	0.67	1.64	0.847	1.02	0.64	1.63	0.926	1.03	0.68	1.57	0.877
Visit*	2.36	1.28	4.35	0.006	1.48	0.81	2.71	0.206	1.94	0.97	3.86	0.060	1.89	1.08	3.32	0.025
AgeXvisit	1.28	0.70	2.33	0.421	1.06	0.59	1.93	0.841	0.78	0.41	1.49	0.455	1.43	0.81	2.52	0.217
-Age in GP samples	0.75	0.47	1.22	0.246	0.74	0.46	1.18	0.203	0.61	0.36	1.03	0.064	0.86	0.68	1.57	0.877

<i>dhps</i> Fixed effects	S436				A437			
	OR	95% CI		<i>P</i>	OR	95% CI		<i>P</i>
Age (10 years) †	1.03	0.69	1.53	0.882	0.81	0.54	1.23	0.336
Season#	1.51	0.93	2.44	0.092	0.71	0.43	1.20	0.205
Visit*	1.53	0.85	2.76	0.154	0.93	0.49	1.77	0.822
AgeXvisit	0.86	0.46	1.58	0.622	1.17	0.61	2.23	0.639
-Age in GP samples	0.88	0.55	1.41	0.603	0.95	0.58	1.57	0.854

† = age centred at 25 years and restricted to ages 15 - 45 years; # low transmission season = 0, high transmission season = 1; *ANC booking = 0, GP = 1;